

Research

Performance Evaluation of Magnifying Glass and Reflector Based Solar Cooker

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Abstract: Both parabolic and box type solar cookers have the potential to be effective and efficient solutions for various challenges related to health, economy, environment, and energy. The research conducted a comprehensive study to develop low-cost and efficient designs for these solar cooker models. To assess their performance, the research measured stagnation temperatures within the cooking chambers, conducted cooking trials, and evaluated the overall performance of different solar cooker types, including one parabolic, three box-type, and one panel cooker. The study also examined the thermal efficiency of these cookers and carried out water boiling and kitchen performance tests. These tests were conducted both with and without the use of heat-retaining materials to better understand the impact of thermal insulation.

Keywords: Improved cook stoves, magnifying glass, Reflector Based solar cooker, renewable energy, biomass energy

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Introduction

Notwithstanding the fact that solar energy holds the potential to meet the global energy demand, it is currently being significantly underutilized. This underutilization can be attributed to the lack of easily accessible techniques and technologies for harnessing solar resources. Presently available solar devices have demonstrated their effectiveness in various applications such as water heating, cooking, drying, distillation, and electricity generation.

Inhabitants of rural and remote communities face ongoing challenges in accessing fundamental necessities like water, food, and energy. The escalating impacts of global warming have exacerbated water scarcity and decreased energy resources available for food preparation. Cooking energy in developing countries' remote regions primarily relies on biomass fuels like firewood and agricultural waste. Unfortunately, the combustion of these resources contributes to detrimental environmental consequences and health issues. Notably, wood burning is a significant source of CO₂ emissions, contributing to the problem of global warming. Unregulated firewood consumption accelerates deforestation, diminishing the carbon absorption capacity of forests. Moreover, the smoke generated during combustion exposes

individuals to various diseases linked to inhalation of pollutants. At present, many prospective research i. e. cancer detection [10], deep learning [11], energy harvesting from solar PV [12] and solar pump [13] are going on for the betterment of mankind. Utilization of solar energy for the purpose of cooking can be beneficial for the people living in rural areas.

In certain arid and remote regions, like deserts, even firewood is scarce. The situation is further compounded in places like Bangladesh, where air pollution presents a major environmental and health crisis, resulting in respiratory infections, heart disease, lung cancer, and birth defects. Indoor air pollution, particularly prominent in developing nations such as Bangladesh, leads to approximately 2 million premature deaths. The capital city, Dhaka, stands out as a prime example with air pollution levels exceeding and six times higher than the recommended level of World Health Organization (WHO).

To address these challenges, the Power Division of the Ministry of Power, Energy and Mineral Resources (MPEMR) has proactively developed a Country Action Plan (CAP). This plan is focused on promoting and disseminating biomass-based fuel-efficient cook stoves to more than 30 million rural households across the country. By introducing cleaner and more efficient cooking technologies, this initiative aims to mitigate the adverse environmental and health impacts associated with traditional biomass-based cooking methods.

Background and Related Work

Renewable energy sources have gained significant attention as a solution to address power scarcity and reduce dependence on finite fossil fuels. Renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, hydroelectric, geothermal, and biomass, offer sustainable alternatives to conventional fossil fuels. Lead acid battery

People utilize less effective mud stoves in Bangladesh's rural areas. Cookstove efficiency is assessed based on both cooking and thermal efficiency [1]. By Bangladesh Bandhu Foundation (BBF) and Infrastructure Development Company Ltd. (IDCOL), improved cook stoves (ICS) powered by biomass are currently being deployed throughout most of the nation [2]. Nearly 2056000 cookstoves were installed by IDCOL and BBF during the period of 2014 -2018[3]. It is being studied whether cookstove waste heat may be used to generate energy. For an ICS prototype, a Peltier module has been constructed in [3]. Authors used thermoelectric generator (TEG) in the cookstoves to produce around 2 volts from wasted heat. The destruction of natural biomass supplies and environmental pollution are brought on by cook stoves which have low thermal efficiency and rudimentary design. Introducing improved cook stoves (ICS) is the ultimate solution. The cook stoves that are created in Bangladesh and have passed international test norms are discussed in [4], including metallic and non-metallic forms. The most effective thermal efficiencies of all kitchen stoves are 35–40% for metallic and 20–30% for non-metallic, according to the significant observation data found by the authors. Bangladesh's energy demand has increased significantly over time due to the country's fast population growth. Among Renewable energy resources, solar energy is one of the highly promising renewable energy sources. At present Bangladesh shares 2.93% renewable energy of total energy ratio which is 650.14MW [5]. Solar cook stoves will be a good option to mitigate biomass energy in Bangladesh. In [6] authors conducted research for developing a mathematical model for solar cookstoves. They designed the stoves by varying absorbance and reflectance of the coating. In [7] author focused on reduction of vulnerability and people's adaptive capability with the utilization of solar cookstoves for rural households.

Solar cookers are eco-friendly and sustainable devices that utilize solar energy for cooking purposes. To enhance their usability and practicality, the integration of lead-acid battery [8] storage systems can play a crucial role in extending cooking hours beyond direct sunlight availability. This literature review aims to explore existing research and studies related to the utilization of lead-acid batteries for solar cookers. Power quality. On the other hand, the growing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly cooking solutions has led to increased adoption of solar cookers. While solar cookers

offer numerous benefits, their integration into the electrical grid raises concerns about potential effects on power quality [9].

Research Methodology

To construct a parabolic Dish solar cooker steel, iron frame, rods were used. A stand made of iron rod was used to set cooking pot on the focus of the parabolic dish. Four box type solar cookers were constructed from different materials. Firstly, a box type solar cooker was designed with tin and a glass cover was used to prevent air cooling. Four reflectors made of stainless steel with convenient sizing were made for focusing the incoming solar irradiation on the cooking pot. The second Box type cooker was constructed with the same materials, but we used different sizing and additionally unlike the first box type solar cooker we have added an extra exposed area in the front. The third box type solar cooker was made from wood. We used a different sizing for this cooker and attached the reflectors to the body of the cooker. The size of the reflectors for box type solar cooker was and glass cover on the top of the cooker has prevented the air cooling of the cooking pot. For fourth box type solar cooker, had an unusual shape and design in compared to the previously described cookers. For this cooker, a square box was made of glass to cover the cooking pot and retain the heat inside the box. Shiny foil was used at the bottom while testing and reflectors were made of anodized aluminum.

Performance Evaluation of the Cookers

Mainly we conducted water boiling tests for each solar cooker. We also conducted several experiments to identify the time required for cooking rice. We kept time and temperature records for each solar cooker and conducted several experiments in different time and weather conditions around the year. Aluminum pots with different sizing are used for cooking. For water boiling tests, the amount of water we used as according to the convenience of the pot sizing. During the performance test of the cookers, we took 100 grams of rice and added double the amount of water for each cooker.

A. Parabolic Dish Solar Cooker

We constructed a parabolic dish cooker with stainless steel. The diameter of this cooker is 40 inches and depth in the center is 10 inches. A stand is attached to the front of the cooker for holding the cooking pot in the focal point of the cooker. A steel pipe is used to make it adjustable toward the sun. This adjustable pipe provides the support to the cooker in getting the maximum exposure of the sun shown in Fig-1.

Fig. 1: Parabolic Dish Solar Cooker

Fig. 2: Box Cooker- 2 side glass

Fig. 3: Box Cooker- 3 side glass

Fig. 4: Box Cooker- Top glass

Fig. 5: Attached Reflector Wooden Box Cooker

B. Box Cooker- 2 side glass

This box type solar cooker is designed with the facility to get sun exposure from top and front. This cooker is square in shape. The top and front exposed areas are covered with regular window glass and areas are 138 sq. inch and 97.75 sq. inch. Reflectors of this solar cooker are made of anodized aluminum. The inner side of the cooker is painted black for enhanced heat absorption rate and better cooking performance shown in Fig-2.

C. Box Cooker- 3 side glass

This box cooker is square in shape, made of 3 sides glass. Reflectors of this solar cooker are made of anodized aluminum shown in Fig-3.

D. Box Cooker- Top glass

This box type solar cooker has only one exposed area on the top (area: 180 sq. inch). Reflectors were made from stainless steel. The inner side of the cooker is painted black for enhanced heat absorption rate and better cooking performance shown in Fig-4.

E. Attached Reflector Wooden Box Cooker

This box type solar cooker has fixed reflector on the top and has an exposed area of 270 sq. inch. Reflectors of this cooker are made from anodized aluminum sheet. Regular glass is used to cover the exposed area of the cooker. The inner side of the cooker is painted black for enhanced heat absorption rate and better cooking performance shown in Fig-5.

Table 1: Dimension for different testing solar cooker

Category	Side	Outer dimension (inches)	Top exposed area (inches)	Front exposed area (inches)	Reflector back (inches)	Reflector Front (inches)	Reflector side 1 (inches)	Reflector side 2 (inches)
Box Cooker- 2 side glass (Reflector material: Anodized aluminum)	Top	17	12	11.5	11.5	22	15	15
	Bottom	17	12	11.5	11.5	22	13.5	13.5
	Side 1	16	11.5	8.5	26	24	18	18
	Side 2	16	11.5	8.5	26	24	18	18
Box Cooker- 3 side glass (Reflector material: Anodized aluminum)	Top	17	12	11.5	11.5	22	15	15
	Bottom	17	12	11.5	11.5	22	15	15
	Side 1	16	11.5	8.5	26	24	18	18
	Side 2	16	11.5	8.5	26	24	18	18
Box Cooker- Top glass (Reflector material: Stainless steel)	Top	20	15	11.5	18	18	15	15
	Bottom	20	15	11.5	18	18	12	12
	Side 1	17	12	8.5	20	20	18	18
	Side 2	17	12	8.5	20	20	18	18
Attached Reflector Wooden Box Cooker	Top	25	9	18	33	33	29	29
	Bottom	25	9	18	23	23	20	20
	Side 1	22	18	15	18	18	18	18
	Side 2	22	18	15	18	18	18	18

Performance Evaluation of the Cookers

A. Test data for Parabolic Dish Solar Cooker

This solar cooker is tested all around the year using several cooking methods and weather conditions to reveal the cooking performance. At first the cooker was used to boil the water. Several data sets were recorded for water boiling performance of the cooker. The highest temperature we recorded was 48.7 °C. After that, we used 100 grams of rice and doubled the amount of water on the cooker for the several times. The highest temperature recorded was 51.9 °C. At last, we tried salt as a heat retainer around the cooking pot. Normally we recorded temperature for one hour the conducted experiments. But for this experiment with salt, we kept the cooker directed to the sun for a longer time.

Maintaining consistency of temperature rise in parabolic dish solar cooker is a major challenge. As the cooking pot is kept in open air, temperature rise stops due to natural air flow. After several trials, we used salt and gravel for heat retaining material for this cooker. Heat retaining materials were kept in a bigger pot and a cooking pot was placed inside that pot. Experiments showed that proper heat retaining capacity enhanced the performance for the cooker. Aluminum

Fig.6: Parabolic Dish Solar Cooker with heat retaining material Salt

Fig.7: Parabolic Dish Solar Cooker with heat retaining material Gravel

Table 2: Test Data

Date	Type of Load	Heat Retainer used	Weather data	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Temperature record	
						Time	temperature
04.03.21	Water	No	32° C			1.35 pm	32.5° C
						1.50 pm	37.5° C
						2.05 pm	42.5° C
						2.20 pm	44.5° C
						2.35 pm	45.3° C
						2.50 pm	43.4° C
05.03.21	Water	No	32° C			11.15 pm	32° C
						11.30 pm	38.5° C
						11.45 pm	44° C
						12.00 pm	46° C
						12.15 pm	48.2° C
						12.30 pm	48.7° C
01.10.21	Water	No	34° C			11.40 pm	31° C
						11.55 pm	38.5° C
						12.10 pm	42.9° C
						12.25 pm	46.9° C
						12.40 pm	46.1° C
23.10.21	Water	No	32° C			12.00 pm	29.3° C
						12.15 pm	40° C
						12.30 pm	44° C
						12.45 pm	44.9° C
						1.12 pm	45.8° C
18.11.21	Water		30° C	456	446	12.00 pm	26.7° C
	Rice 100 gm					12.15 pm	33.9° C
						12.30 pm	38.1° C

						12.45 pm	46.9° C
						1.00 pm	49.5° C
						1.20 pm	51.9° C
20.11.21	Water	salt	30° C	420	410	12.15 pm	26.5° C
	Rice 100gm					2.20 pm	51.6° C
21.11.21	Water	Gravel	30° C	418	408	11.15 pm	26.1° C
	Rice 100gm					3.00 pm	45.1° C

B. Test data for Box type solar cooker: We tested different type fo box cooker throughtout the year and analysed the performce of the cooker.

Table 3: Box Type Solar Cooker

Box Cooker- 2 side glass (Reflector material: Anodized aluminum)								
Date	Type of load	Heat retainer used	Weather data	Initial weight (gm)	Final weight (gm)	Weight diff. (gm)	Temperature record	
							Time	Temperature
23.10.21	Water	No	32 ° C	540			12.10 pm	29.3° C
	Rice (150 gm)						1.10 pm	43° C
17.11.21	water	No	31 ° C	876	860	16	11.00 am	26.9° C
							12.00 pm	42.5° C
17.11.21	Water						12.30 pm	26.9° C
	Rice 100gm	Sand	31 ° C	468	480		1.30 pm	45.2° C
18.11.21	Water		30 ° C				12.30 pm	26.9 ° C
	Rice 100 gm	Gravel		476	468	8	1.30 pm	53.4° C
Box Cooker- 3 side glass (Reflector material: Anodized aluminum)								
26.09.21	Water	No	36 ° C	10194	1.180	14	11.40 am	30.9 ° C
							12.40 pm	51.8° C
01.10.21	Water	No	34 ° C	994	984	10	11.40 pm	31° C
							12.40 pm	49.5° C
23.10.21	Water	No	32 ° C	546	656		12.20 pm	29.3 ° C
	Rice (150 gm)						1.20 pm	48.8° C
17.11.21	Water	No	31 ° C	1054	1044	10	11.00 am	26.9° C
							12.00 pm	42.5° C
17.11.21	Water		31 ° C	472	480		12.35 pm	26.9° C
	Rice 100gm	Gravel					1.30 pm	45.5° C
18.11.21	Water	Sand	30° C	470	462	8	12.00 pm	26.7° C
	Rice 100 gm						1.00 pm	58.6° C
21.11.21	Water		30 ° C	472	484		11.15 am	26.1° C
	Rice 100 gm	Gravel					3.00 pm	53.6° C
Box Cooker- Top glass (Reflector material: Stainless steel)								
17.11.21	Water	No	31 ° C	400	392	8	12.20pm	25 ° C
							1.28 pm	59.7 ° C
18.11.21	Water	No	30 ° C	500	492	8	10.28 am	26 ° C

							11.44 am	73.5 ° C
Attached Reflector Wooden Box Cooker								
23.10.21	Water	No	30 ° C	542	658		12.10 pm	29.3° C
	Rice (150gm)						1.10 pm	52.9° C

Box Cooker- 2 side glass was tested with 150 grams of rice and 0.2 liter of water for checking its performance. The highest recorded temperature was 43 without the usage of any heat retaining materials. Performance is better when we tested with the heat retaining material like sand and gravel, the maximum temperature recorded was 45.2 and 53.4° C.

With same amount of rice and water tested in Box Cooker- 3 side glass. The highest recorded temperature was 51.8° C without the usage of any heat retaining materials. Performance is better when we tested with the heat retaining material like sand and gravel, the maximum temperature recorded was 58.6° C and 53.6° C.

The same test was performed using Box Cooker- Top glass and maximum temperature observed 73.5 ° C while in Attached Reflector Wooden Box Cooker showed 52.9° C.

On the other hand, Parabolic dish solar cookers are eco-friendly. Cooked foods in it are nutritious and hygienic. Other than this, parabolic dish cookers need frequent adjustments of the angle and direction and require relatively bigger space. Initial cost of the parabolic may be high but using a solar parabolic dish cooker can be economical in the long run. For improvements, heat retaining cooking pot can be used. Different reflector materials can be used, and sun-tracking devices can be included.

Compared to parabolic dish cookers, box cookers consist of a glass box for covering the cooking pot. Glass box is used to trap the heat inside it. It is small and cost-effective in design. For improvements, heat retaining cooking pot can be used. Different reflector materials can be used, and sun-tracking devices can be included.

Our designed wooden box type solar cooker is an eco-friendly tool to utilize the sun light for cooking. Wood is used instead of stainless steel in this model for minimizing initial cost. It has a high acceptance angle and high tolerance for tracking error. For improvements, heat retaining cooking pot can be used. Different reflector materials can be used, and sun-tracking devices can be included.

This is also a box type solar cooker which includes a glass cover on the top. There is a scope for tightly adjusting the glass cover to trap the light. As a result, it can retain the heat. It can only use the direct sunlight falling on its top. Comparatively, it requires less space. It also has a high acceptance angle and high tolerance for tracking error. For improvements, heat retaining cooking pot can be used. Different reflector materials can be used, and sun-tracking devices can be included.

In future both parabolic and box type solar cooker can also be useful to disinfect Contaminated water or milk. Box type solar cookers can be utilized as the solar dryers for drying Spices, Fruits, Pickles, Fish etc.

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